

COMMON ENGLISH GRAMMAR MISTAKES AMONG ENGLISH LEARNERS

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Annotation: *This article presents different english grammar mistakes among English Learners and pay attention the clear problems.*

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The English language is well known for being the language of international communication in the modern world – and wherever you originate from, and whatever native tongue you speak, it's likely that learning English will be invaluable in both your personal and professional lives. Of course, the English language frequently frustrates new learners with various grammatical hurdles and stumbling blocks.

Here are common English grammar mistakes:

1. Present and Past Tenses
2. Your/You're
3. There/Their/There're
4. Confusing similar spellings and words
5. Using incomplete comparisons

1. Present and Past Tense

Present Tenses in English are used to talk about the present, and the future and to summarise a book, play or film when telling a story in the present tense.

There 4 present tense forms in the English language:

1. Present Simple. I learn
2. Present Continuous. I'm learning
3. Present Perfect. I have learned
4. Present Perfect Continuous. I have been learning.

Most students can not differ from present and Past Tenses. Learners can use the past tense to talk about events and situations that have finished. Apart from this, they can also use past tense in English to talk about long-standing events and

situations that have already happened in the past. For example, When I was a child, I lived in the village. Learners should pay attention their mistakes and they focus on how to get rid of them. If they practice daily, they can keep up with.

2. Your/You're

Learners may have trouble in these words also. They sometimes can not differ from these words.

"YOUR" indicates a possession-and defines that something belongs to you.

"You're" is short for "You are". Learners tend to mix them, and this is commonly mistake among elementary students.

Learners mustn't use these:

Your clever.

Do you know where your going?

You pen is long.

How to get it right:

You're clever.

Do you know where you're going?

Your pen is long.

3. There/Their/They're

These pesky homophones look like a little bit of a headache.

Rules: Learners should use "There" when they refer to how owns something-showing that something belongs to that person. And also they can use "They're" is a shortened version of "They are".

Learners mustn't use:

Their going to be here soon.

We should contact they're friend.

They friend is from Uzbekistan.

You can go Their.

Here is how you use these words correctly:

They're going to be here soon.

We should contact their friend.

Their friend is from Uzbekistan.

You can go there.

4. Confusing similar spellings and words

The English language is quite rich in words. What I mean by this is that a lot of sounds are similar, or spelled similarly, but which have different meanings and need to be used in different contexts. Perhaps the most common stumbling block experienced by learners who are learning English as a second language is making sure to use the right word in the right context, rather than a similar but improper ones. The only way to avoid this issue is to learn which words fit in which context, on a case-by-case basis and also practice.

Here are some words people often mix up:

“Two,” “too,” and “to”

“Here” and “hear”

“Your” and “you’re”

“Weather” and “whether”

5. Using incomplete comparisons.

Many words in the English language imply a comparison - and using them without completing the comparison is being a common grammatical mistake.

Here's an example:

I'm older

It was much colder

You were cleverer.

To make this grammatically correct, you would need to complete this comparison.

Here's examples:

"I'm older than Marjona"

"It is much colder than yesterday"

"You were cleverer than me"

If learners pay attention to these mistakes and try to analyze, they will not make mistake on this subject any more. Without any doubt, practice makes perfect.

Grammar and punctuation are essential in the English language and gaining confidence in how to avoid any grammatical errors is a valuable part of your learning journey. You should practice developing your grammar daily; it will help you to become a confident writer with a firm grasp on the English language.

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